

Ethnomedicinal Plants Used in Gujarat For the Treatment of Various Diseases

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ABSTRACT

India's traditional medicine, which is based on medicinal plants, exhibits a strong connection to healthy living, diet, and folk healing practices recognized by a particular community. The current study's objective is to conduct an ethnobotanical review of the medicinal plants used as traditional medicine in Gujarat, including details on plant species, sections used and therapeutic applications. Information was gathered and used to support previously published data about medicinal plant pharmacology in journals and books. The inventoried plant species in the current work are frequently used for the treatment of various illnesses and to ensure the medication safety of local people. Studies on these ethno-medicinal plants would be helpful for the preservation of traditional medical knowledge as well as the discovery of new plant-based drug compounds that exhibit enormous pharmacological value. Information on these plants could be obtained from traditional medicine practitioners and tribal people of the Aravalli district.

Keywords: Ethnomedicinal plants, Diseases treatment, Gujarat

INTRODUCTION

Scientific literature of this field has grown quickly as a result of increased research activity in the areas of discovery, isolation, application, and examinations of the efficacy of herbal medicines. Numerous prestigious journals, especially those in the field of Integrative and Complementary Medicine, publish articles on this topic with high levels of scholarly interest (I&C Medicine). Any study field should periodically be viewed from a wider angle, based on pertinent publications, their quantitative and qualitative indicators, and the dominating trends within the field. Such summaries are crucial for enhancing researchers' publishing productivity, modifying journal editorial policies, and assisting researchers in better understanding the current state of affairs in the relevant field in order to plan their future research, which is typically conceived as an expansion of prior work in the field. One of the fundamental requirements for raising the standard of research in this field is the requirement for such periodic reviews of the literature in ethnopharmacology and herbal medicine (Albuquerque and Hanazaki, 2009).

There are several written reports from Asia attesting to the therapeutic value of Himalayan plants. The Vedas provide evidence of perhaps the first recorded use of herbal plants. The oldest known collection of human knowledge was created between 4500 and 600 B.C., and it consists of 67 plant species. Ayurveda, a school of traditional medicine that is popular in India and Nepal, offers additional information regarding the therapeutic use of substances other than herbal medicines (Manabdhar, 1980). However, only a small portion of the plant species on Earth (250,000–500,000) have been investigated phytochemically or studied for their pharmacological properties, aside from ethnobotanical/ethnomedicinal research that has documented the pharmacological properties of plants and random screenings of a number of species for their biological activities (Rates, 2001). The use of medicinal plants has gained widespread attention and has implications for global health. The upkeep of the global healthcare system for the large population has been greatly aided by herbal medicine (Akerle, 1988). This is significantly improved in less developed or developing nations, where the use of

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traditional medicine was halted throughout history. Both emerging and developed nations have increased their understanding of the medicinal properties of plants (WHO, 1998). When the eighteenth century first began, more than 80% of medicine was Particularly following the scientific revolution, the field of herbal medicine has influenced the development of the pharmaceutical business, where synthetic medications are now readily available (Shinwari and Qaiser, 2011). Due to the fact that plants or their derivatives are regarded as safe and effective medications with minimal side effects and low cost (Chalannavar *at el.*, 2013), medicinal plants are used more frequently in the treatment of diseases. The knowledge of alternative medicine based on the use of plants in treatment represents an inheritance passed from generation to generation over centuries, either verbally or in writing, keeping in mind that the traditional inheritance may be facing extinction if it is not transmitted to the next generation and is still limited to the former only (Schulze, 2017). This review shows that numerous plant species are crucial to regional healing practices and that traditional medical knowledge is still practiced and has a big impact on tribals residing in Gujarat. The documenting of this extensive body of traditional

ethno-medical knowledge has given us new knowledge that will not only help to recognize this previously unrecognized knowledge but may also open up new directions for pharmacological research to advance treatment for a variety of illnesses. The current review was conducted to gather information about the plants used by people of Gujarat in traditional medicine, such as to highlight the description of medicinal plants including botanical name, common name, disease and the area in which it is utilized.

Result and Discussion

The present survey reported 65 diseases which are being cured by many plant species of various localities of Gujarat belonging to different families. The most cured disease of all is fever and skin disease which are being cured by 17 plant species. Followed by dysentery, abdominal disease and rheumatoid arthritis which are cured by 15 different plant species. The least plant species curing plants reported were for diseases such as Beri-Beri, tetanus, night blindness, filariasis, gonorrhoea, leprosy, migraine, mumps etc. (Patel and Patel, 2013).

Table: 1 List Ethnomedicinal plant species which is used for different types of disease

No	Diseases	Scientific Name Of Plant	Common Name	Area	Refrence
1.	Asthma	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Piplo	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Som, Sandhiaval		
		<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Ardusi	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (Linn.) Corr.	Bili	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (Linn.) R. Br	Akdo		
		<i>Bahunia racemosa</i> Lam.	Zinji	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br.	Akdo		
		<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Umro		
		<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	Tentu	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021

		<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Salai gugal		
		<i>Solanum indicum</i> L.	Ubhi ringani	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Datura inoxia</i> Mil L.	Kalo dhaturu	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Venivel		
		<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Ardusi		
2.	Abdominal disease	<i>Senna auriculata</i> (L.) Roxb	Avad	Sasan Gir	Solanki at el.,2020
		<i>Cassia fistula</i> (L.)	Garmalo		
		<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb.	Kuvadiyo		
		<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> Roxb.	Sisam		
		<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb	Baheda	Kaprada	Patel at el., 2020
		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Khakhro	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr.	Bili	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roth	Bahedo	Narmada	Yadav at el., 2013
		<i>Balanites egyptica</i> (L.) DeL.	Ingoro	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Punica grantum</i> L.	Dadam		
		<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Divel		
		<i>Oxystelma secamone</i> (L.) Karst.	Jal dudhi		
3.	Beri	<i>Celastruspaniculatas</i> Willd.	Malkankta	Sasan Gir	Solanki at el.,2020
4.	Bone fracture	<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L) Huth	Tuver	Sasan Gir	Solanki at el.,2020
		<i>Combretumovalifolium</i> Roxb. EX G. Don.	Madvelo		
		<i>Madhuca indica</i> GmeL.	Mahudo	Kaprada	Patel at el., 2020
		<i>Delonix elata</i> (L.) Gamble.	Sandesaro	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012

		<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L	Khati amla	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
		<i>Combretum ovalifolium</i> Roxb.	Dhamas	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Millsp.	Tuver		
5.	Body pain	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Maradsing	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb.	Guggal	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
6.	Boils	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Satodi	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forsk.) Edgew.	Kerdo		
		<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) W. & A.	Kini		
		<i>Euphorbia caducifolia</i> Hains	Thor		
		<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Som, Sandhiaval	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Grangea maderaspatana</i> (L.) Poir.	Jalbhagri		
7.	Bronchitis	<i>Taverniera cuneifolia</i> (Roth) Arn.	Jathi madh	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Sterculia urens</i> Roxb	Kadayo		
		<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Som, Sandhiaval H		
		<i>Solanum virginianum</i> L.	Bhoi ringani	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Holarrehena antidyentrica</i> WalL.	Kurchi	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm.f.	Bhotingdi	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb.) W. & A.	Pani sadad		
8.	Cancer	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> L.	Kachnar	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020
		<i>Momordica charantia</i> (L.)	Karela		
		<i>Aeglemarmelos</i> (L) Correa	Bili		

		<i>Annona squamosa</i> (L.)	Sitafal		
		<i>Santalum album</i> L.	Chandan		
		<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Limdo		
		<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Hook.f. & Thomson	Gado		
		<i>Vanda tessellata</i>	Vanda	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
9.	Cough	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Moto arduso	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel and Patel, 2013
		<i>Echinops echinatus</i> Roxb.	Utkanto		
		<i>Capparis cartilaginea</i> Decne.	Parvati rai	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forsk.) Edgew.	Kerdo		
		<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Lamk.) Roynal	Mamecho		
		<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb.	Jungali jamphal	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Bahunia racemosa</i> Lam.	Zinji	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br.	Akdo		
		<i>Tabernaemontana undulata</i>	Ragatro hido	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Baheda		
		<i>Maerua oblongifolia</i> (Forsk.) A. Rich	Jethimadh	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
10.	Cholera	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Limdo	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Nagod	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
11.	Constipation	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Baheda	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Harde		

		<i>Senna italica</i> Miller	Sona mukhi	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
12.	Colic complaints	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br.	Akdo	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
13.	Diabetes	<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.)	Gugar	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Lamk.) Roynal	Mamecho		
		<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) W.T. Aiton	White akdo	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Merremia turpethum</i> (L.) Rendle	Nahotar na vela		
		<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Satavari		
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Umro		
		<i>Gymnema sylvestris</i> (Retz) Schult.	Madhunashini	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (Roxb). Benth	Bili	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
		<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (Linn) Skeels.	Jambu		
<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> Roxb.	Arjun sadad				
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Nag charo	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019		
14.	Diarrhea	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Garmalo	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel and Patel, 2013
		<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.)	Jambu		
		<i>Fagonia schweienfurthii</i> (Hadidi)	Javaso	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Indoneesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem	Karyatu		
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (Linn.) Corr.	Bili	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Bahunia racemosa</i> Lam.	Zinji	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002

		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Khakhro		
		<i>Cassia auticulata</i> L.	Aval		
		<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Maradshing		
		<i>Zizyphus nummularia</i> (Burm. F.) W.&A.	Chani bor		
		<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Harde	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Terminalia crenulata</i> Roth	Sadad	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
15.	Dysentery	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Shatavari	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R. Br.	Nano Akado		
		<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.)	Gugar		
		<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forsk.) Fiori	Ser gangani		
		<i>Indoneesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem	Karyatu		
		<i>Pentatropis spiralis</i> (Forsk.) Decne	Dhodhiyal, Dhodheji Val		
		<i>Adansonia digitata</i> Linn.	Baobab	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (Linn.) Corr.	Bili		
		<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd	Satavari		
		<i>Adansonia digitata</i> L.	Gorakh amlo	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Bahunia racemosa</i> Lam.	Zinji		
		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Khakhro		
		<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i> Roxb.	Timru		
		<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Maradshing		
<i>Terminalia crenulata</i> Roth	Sadad	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> ,		
16.	Earache	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.)	Nani Khapat	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010

		<i>Capparis cartilaginea</i> Decne.	Parvati rai	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020
		<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Trigharivel	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Cassia auticulata</i> L.	Aval	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Maradshing		
		<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	Nagod		
				<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Saragvo
17.	Eczema	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> Linn.	Chanothi	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Argemone maxicana</i> Linn.	Darudi		
		<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Limdo		
18.	Eye complaints	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Aloe vera</i> (Linn.) Burm	Kuvarpanthu	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L) Diels.	Vevdi	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> W. & A.	Dodi		
19.	Fever	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Garmalo	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel & Patel (2013)
		<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Moto arduso		
		<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Lamk.) Roynal	Mamecho	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Indoneesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem	Karyatu		
		<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Som, Sandhiaval		
		<i>Caesalpinia crista</i> L.	Kachika	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020
		<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> (WalL.) ex G. Don	Indrajav		
		<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L) Pers.	Agathio	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	Nagod				

		<i>Aloe vera</i> (Linn.) Burm	Kuvarpathu	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Brum. f.) WalL.	Kariyathu		
		<i>Mitragyna parvifolia</i> (Roxb.) Korth	Kalam	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
		<i>Holarhena antidysenterica</i> Wall	Kalokado	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Anogeissus sericea</i> Brandis.	Anarak Dhavado		
		<i>Encostema hyssopifolium</i> Verdoon	Mamejvo		
		<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	Tulsi		
		<i>Caesalpinia crista</i> L.	Kaski		
20.	Filariases	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Trigharivel	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
21.	Gastric troubles	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R. Br.	Nano Akado	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Capparis cartilaginea</i> Decne.	Parvati rai		
		<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forsk.) Edgew.	Kerdo		
		<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (L.) Soland.	Truja Val, Tru Val		
		<i>Indoneesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem	Karyatu		
		<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd	Satavari	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
22.	Gonorrhoea	<i>Sterculia urens</i> L.	Kadayo	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
23.	Hair problems	<i>Millettia pinnata</i> (L.) Panigrahi	Karanj	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Senegalia rugata</i> (Lam.) Britton & Rose	Shikakai		
		<i>Sapindus laurifolius</i> Vahl.	Aritha		
		<i>Eclipta prostrate</i> L.	Bhangro	Godhra	

		<i>Anona squamosal</i> L.	Anduri		Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
24.	Headache	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Shatavari	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Saragvo	Kaprada	
		<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	Nagod	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Blumia eriantha</i> DC.	Pilo bhangro	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
25.	Heart attack	<i>Pterocarpusmarsupium</i> Roxb.	Biyo	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020
		<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> Roxb.	Arjun sadad	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
26.	Hepatic problems	<i>Aloe barbedensis</i> Mill.	Kuvarpathu	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm. f.	Bhoringani		
27.	Hysteria	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Garmalo	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel & Patel 2013
		<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Moto arduso		
28.	Infertility	<i>Cavaponia lasiniosa</i> (L.) C. Jeffrey	Shivlingi	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020
29.	Intestinal worms	<i>Moringa concanensis</i> Nimmo	Jungli Saragvo	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel & Patel (2013)
		<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Lamk.) Roynal	Mamecho	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Kuntze.	Khakhro	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> Linn.	Vad		
		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Khakhro	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Luffa echinata</i> Roxb	Kukadvel	Arvalli	
30.	Indigestion	<i>Pentatropis spiralis</i> (Forsk.) Decne	Dhodhiyal, Dhodheji Val	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> (WalL.) ex G. Don	Indrajav	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020
		<i>Musa x paradistica</i> L.	Kel		

		<i>Adansonia digitata</i> Linn.		Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
31.	Jaundice	<i>Moringa concanensis</i> Nimmo	Jungli Saragvo	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel & Patel (2013)
		<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (L.) Soland.	Truja Val, Tru Val	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Maytenus emarginata</i> (Willd.) D. Hou	Vingo	Bhuj, Kachchh	
		<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> (Linn.) Vent.	Tetu	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Luffa echinata</i> Roxb	Kukadvel	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> (L.) Vent.	Tentu		
		<i>Lufa sylendrica</i> (L.) M.J. Roem.	Galka	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Maytenus emarginata</i> (Willd.) D.Hou.	Vikalo		
		<i>Phyllanthus frateruns</i> Webst.	Bhoi amla		
32.	Joint pain	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb. ex Sm.	Savan	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Aloe barbedensis</i> Mill.	Kuvarpathu		
33.	Kidney stone	<i>Citrusmedica</i> L.	Bijoru	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Umro		
		<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Lam.) Oken	Panphutti	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Lanbadi		
34.	Leprosy	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urb.	Bhrami	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
35.	Leukoderma	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R. Br.	Nano Akado	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , (2010)
		<i>Argemone maxicana</i> Linn.	Darudi	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Chanothi	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) Schult.	Anantmul	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019

36.	Leukorrhea	<i>Maerua oblongifolia</i> (Foeak.) A. Rich.	Pinjaro	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Bahunia racemosa</i> Lam.	Zinji	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
37.	Migraine	<i>Capparis trifoliata</i> Roxb	Bhatudi	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
38.	Mouth ulcer	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.)	Nani Khapat	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Capparis cartilaginea</i> Decne.	Parvati rai		
		<i>Abrus precatorious</i> (L.)	Chanothi	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> Forst.	Gunda	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Roxb. Ex. RottL.) willd	Kher	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Salai gugal	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Vachellia nilotica</i>	Desi baval		
39.	Menstruation problem	<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i> L.	Jasud	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
40.	Mumps	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Umro	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
41.	Night blindness	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L) Pers.	Khakharvel	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
42.	Paralysis	<i>Celastrus paniculata</i> Willd	Jyotishmati	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
43.	Piles	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Baheda	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Anghedi	Dahod	Maru and Patel 2012
		<i>Launaea sarmentosa</i> (Willd.) Alst.	Thikari	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
44.	Rabies	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Haldar	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i> L.	Thor		
45.	Respiratory problems	<i>Vincetoxicum indicum</i> (Burm.f.). mabb	Damvel	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
46.	Rheumatoid arthritis	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R. Br.	Nano Akado	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.)	Gugar		

		<i>Abrus precatorius</i> Linn.	Chanothi		
		<i>Calatropis gigantea</i> (Linn.) R. Br	Akdo	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Celastrus paniculata</i> Willd.	Jyotishmati		
		<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Chanothi		
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili		
		<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (L.f.) Wang	Ankol	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br.	Akdo		
		<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam	Saragavo		
		<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Salai gugal	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Vanda tessellata</i>	Vanda		
		<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb.	Salai gugal	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
		<i>Madhuca indica</i> Roxb.	Mahudo		
		<i>Moringa concanensis</i> Nimmo	Gando saragvo	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
47.	Ring worm	<i>Pergularia damia</i> (Forsk.) Chiov.	Nagala dudhi		
		<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.)	Jambu	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel and Patel, 2013
		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Mucuna prurita</i> (L) DC.	Bhair		
		<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Khati ambli	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Zizyphus mauritiana</i> Lam.	Bordi		
		<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.)	Jambu	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel and Patel, 2013
		<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.)	Gugar		
		<i>Lycium barbarum</i> L.	Garothi	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
49.	Skin disease	<i>Senegalia catechu</i> (L.f.) P.J.H. Hunter & Mabb.	Khair	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> ,2020

		<i>Millettia pinnata</i> (L.) Panigrahi	Karanj		
		<i>Abrus precator ious</i> (L.)	Chanothi		
		<i>Vachellia nilotica</i> (L.) P.J.H. Hunter & Mabb.	Desi baval		
		<i>Santalum album</i> L.	Chandan		
		<i>Celastrus paniculata</i> Willd	Malkanki	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Luffa echinata</i> Roxb	Kukadvel		
		<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Harde	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Vachellia nilotica</i>	Desi baval		
		<i>Gmelia arborea</i>	Seven		
		<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> Spreng.	Charoli	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
		<i>Madhuca indica</i> Roxb.	Mahudo		
		<i>Morinda tomentosa</i> Hook. f.	Aledi	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
		<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Kalo Dhaturo		
		<i>Salvadora persica</i> L.	Piludi		
<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Haldar				
50.	Snake Bite	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Shatavari	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Abelmoschus moschatus</i> Linn.	Okra	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb.	Seven	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013
51.	Stomach ache	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Shatavari	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Indigofera oblongifolia</i> Forsk.	Zeel		
		<i>Senegalia catechu</i> (L.f.) P.J.H. Hunter & Mabb.	Khair	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Maradshing	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Khakhro	Narmada	Yadav <i>at el.</i> , 2013

		<i>Carissa carandas</i> L.	Karamda	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
52.	Stye	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Trigharivel	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
53.	Swelling	<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forsk.) Fiori	Ser gangani	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i> L.f.	Arani		
		<i>Aloe barbedensis</i> Mill.	Kuvarpathu	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Celastrus paniculata</i> Willd	Jyotishmati		
		<i>Erythrina variegata</i> Linn.	Panarvo		
		<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> (Roxb.) D.C	Khakharvel	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Wrightia tinktoria</i> R. Br.	Dudheli	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> Wall. ex Bedd.	Dhavado				
54.	Sunstroke	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Shatavari	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.	Kakdi	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forsk.) Fiori	Sunstroke	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Blumia eriantha</i> DC.	Ambo	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
55.	Syphilis	<i>Tabernaemontana undulata</i>	Ragatro hido	Sabarkantha	Mevada <i>at el.</i> , 2021
		<i>Sterculia urens</i>	Kadayo		
56.	Tetanus	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L) Corr.	Bili	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
57.	Toothache	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.)	Nani Khapat	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (L.) Soland.	Truja Val, Tru Val		
		<i>Millettia pinnata</i> (L.) Panigrahi	Karanj	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Erythrina variegata</i> Linn.	Panarvo	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
58.	Tuberculosis	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i> (L.) DeL.	Hingoriyo	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010

		<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> (Roxb.) Nees	Vas	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> (Rets.) Willd.	Vas	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
59.	Tympanites	<i>Cassia auriculata</i> L.	Avar	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
60.	Typhoid	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> L.	Takmariya	Godhra	Gadhvi and Modi, 2019
61.	Urinary disorders	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Shatavari	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
		<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) W. & A.	Kini		
		<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> (Linn.) Vent.	Tetu	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Saragvo		
62.	Urticaria	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Khakhro	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
63.	Vomiting	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> L.	Jambu	Poshina, Sabarkantha	Patel and Patel, 2013
		<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> Linn.	Tulsi	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Cassia auriculata</i> L.	Aval	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
64.	Weakness	<i>Maytenus emarginata</i> (Willd.) D. Hou	Vingo	Bhuj, Kachchh	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2010
65.	Wound	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Gha jadvu	Sasan Gir	Solanki <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (Linn.) R. Br	Akdo	Kaprada	Patel <i>at el.</i> , 2020
		<i>Erythrina variegata</i> Linn.	Panarvo	Kaprada	
		<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Roxb. Ex. RottL.) willd	Kher	Arvalli	Punjani, 2002
		<i>Adinacordifilia</i> (Roxb.) Bth. & Hk.	Haldarvo		
		<i>Typha angustata</i> Bory & Chaub.	Ghabajariyo		
		<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	Nagod		

Graph 1. Disease treated by different plants

CONCLUSION

It is safe to say that scientific interest in ethnobotanical research is growing, and herbal medicine is widely acknowledged as an alternative/complementary therapy of great significance for human health and well-being, based on the analysis of the scientific literature that has been published over the past many years. It appears that many prestigious publications have opened their pages to publishing studies on ethnobotany and herbal therapy that are supported by facts and are backed by science. This study indicates that wild plants are commonly used as health treatments in this region as it provides an inventory of medicinal plants used in a rural area by different tribes. The information gathered could prevent the loss of traditional knowledge about the use of medicinal plants that traditional healers have preserved. It also provides the necessary background data for a potential phytochemical study on the most commonly used plants. These studies focus a lot on the plants that are utilized as traditional herbal medicines in many nations. Yet, in some nations, ethnobotanical research has been employed to uncover new medical applications and the expansion of the pharmaceutical industry.

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